

Additional file 2: Table S1

Preparation of the worms		Preparation of the bacteria
Day 1	Bleaching <i>phb-2(tm2998)/mIn1;Phsp-6::GFP</i>	Inoculate RNAi library in LB agar O/N 37°C
Day 2	Place starved L1s in liquid OP50 20°C, 120 rpm	
Day 3		Replicate RNAi library in deep well plates O/N 37°C, 180 rpm
Day 4	Sorting L2s <i>phb-2(tm2998);Phsp-6::GFP</i>	Bacterial culture and resuspend in complete S medium
Day 5	Incubate 20°C, 120 rpm	
Day 6	Imaging	